

Assessment of Leadership Styles and Engagement of Local Student Government

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ABSTRACT

Each educational institution in the Philippines has student leaders involved in various extra-curricular activities, including councils and governments. The Local Student Government (LSG) provides a platform for students to develop leadership skills and participate in decision-making processes. Leadership is crucial for organizational success, with different styles such as autocratic, democratic, transactional, transformational, and laissez-faire impacting team morale and effectiveness. Identifying the optimal leadership styles for LSGs that can impact the student government effectiveness, member participation, and overall engagement. By conducting surveys and interviews with local student government key officials, the research seeks to identify which leadership styles foster a positive environment for student involvement, decision-making, and community building. Overall, respondents in the study showed a preference for democratic and transactional leadership styles, highlighting the importance of effective leadership in student organizations as it was characterized by vision, inspiration, and individual consideration, greater involvement and satisfaction among members. The researchers recommend organizing seminars on leadership styles, electing key officials to strengthen democratic values, formalizing responsibilities, and emphasizing holistic development through training on topics like finance and stress management. They suggest avoiding micromanagement, allowing personnel to create projects, fostering a family-like culture with rewards and recognition, and maintaining low turnover by reducing workload pressures. Additionally, interviews should include questions about leadership style preferences, and the study should be replicated in different settings for further insights.

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

Each and every educational institution in the Philippines have student-leaders or those that have leadership roles as their extra-curricular activities during their studies. Some establish their own clubs or organizations relevant to their interests or hobby, while others participate in councils and governments. The Local Student Government (LSG) serves as a vital platform for students to develop leadership skills, foster a sense of community, and participate in decision-making processes within their educational institutions. Organizational success or failure has always been correlated with leadership, and certain surveys indicate that an organization's performance may be attributed to the quality and efficacy of its leadership team as much as 45% of the time (Gutterman, 2023)- and student governments are no exception. Leadership is similar to a light that gives clear direction other people's efforts to accomplish a goal (Kruse, 2013). Finding the right leadership style for a company can help a leader pave the way for success. This approach will specify how a leader directs, motivates, and supervises the people they manage (Feder, 2022). According to Gavin (2019), a recent study by the international consulting firm DDI indicated that businesses that invest in training staff members with strong leadership potential have a four times higher financial success rate than those that don't. While an organization may have people with various talents and capabilities, it is leadership that harnesses individual efforts toward the collective goal (Indeed Editorial Team, 2024). Professionals are pushing leaders at all levels to possess the ability to manage talent in order to boost engagement. Choosing the right leadership style or knowing how to increase the level of engagement with the workforce is an important key in preventing a disengaged workforce (Batista-Taran, et.al, 2013). The effectiveness of these student bodies largely depends on the leadership styles adopted by their leaders. There are a lot of leadership styles that can be implemented to an organization. Leadership style is the manifestation of a leader's leadership approach. It describes how a leader decides to guide and engage with their subordinates, make choices, convey expectations, and establish a work environment (Bwalya, 2023). Each of these approaches has advantages and disadvantages that can affect team morale, culture, and the organization as a whole.

The study aims to explore the correlation between leadership styles and student engagement within the LSGs through examining various leadership approaches, such as autocratic, democratic, transactional, transformational, and laissez-faire. Those are leadership styles common in most literatures, brief descriptions are hereby indicated: Autocratic leadership style places great value on the person in charge's input and decision-making.; Democratic leadership places a strong emphasis on team members making decisions together.; Laissez-faire leadership lets team members operate independently by taking a hands-off approach (Parsons, 2024); Transformational leadership is a leadership style that prioritizes change and transformation; and Transactional leadership, often referred to as managerial leadership, is a leadership style that depends on rewards and penalties (IMD, 2024). Through this research, it is hoped that valuable insights will be gained into the optimal leadership styles for LSGs. These findings can inform the training and development of LSG leaders, enhance their effectiveness, and ultimately contribute to a more engaged and thriving student community.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Autocratic Leadership

An autocracy is a system of governance where a single ruler has all authority and makes all of the decisions. Autocracies have existed in the form of absolute monarchy and dictatorships since the ancient era, when kings and emperors governed over vast nations and tribal territories. Academics frequently associate autocracy and totalitarian governments to the likes of Adolf Hitler in Germany and Josef Stalin in the Soviet Unions. Autocratic leadership became popular when people accepted the authority of strong leaders who might seize control of their nations during periods of political instability. In fact, the 15th-century Italian political scholar, Niccolo Machiavelli, recommended autocracy as a short-term solution to restore political order and end discontent (National Geographic Society, 2023).

Autocratic leaders usually make decisions based on their own thoughts and opinions, often disregarding input from their followers. This style of leadership entails complete, authoritarian authority over a group (Cherry, 2023). A leader that practices autocratic leadership exercises total control over their team members and expects total compliance from them (Ahmed and Simha (2023). This type of leadership has its fair share of advantages. One of the key advantages of autocratic leadership is its ability to enable swift decision-making without the need for lengthy consultations with others (Sindakis, 2023). Another benefit of autocratic leadership is the clear direction and structure it provides within the organization. With a strong leader in charge, employees understand their roles and responsibilities, which helps streamline processes and ensures that everyone is aligned toward shared goals (Mansaray, 2019).

Of course, there is also a fair share of disadvantages within this certain leadership style. One of the main disadvantages of this kind of leadership is that it hinders the creativity and personal growth of each member of the organization. Also, it lowers the team's morale as autocratic leaders can often build up resentment, fears of failure, and apathy among their people if they are too authoritarian (Malec, 2022). Another significant disadvantage is that it stifles employee creativity and innovation. Because leaders make all decisions without seeking input from team members, they may overlook valuable insights and suggestions (Briker et al., 2020). If a team depends exclusively on their leader's perspectives, they may overlook critical information or opportunities. Teams should leverage the unique strengths of their members and apply them in various situations. By controlling too much of the decision-making process, autocratic leaders can frequently hinder the progress of their organizations.

Many people see autocratic leadership style as outdated. However, this leadership style is still alive and applied and recognized up to the modern day in many states and different organizations (Maseti and Gumede, 2011). There are certain time and scenarios that a leader of an organization needs to exhibit autocratic principle. Autocratic methods work well, particularly when workers are inexperienced or new. Exercising authoritarian management style is recommended to provide precise instructions and directives to these early teams or workforce. The same method is also employed during times of chasing deadlines, urgent decision-making, and producing outputs without errors (Brown, 2024). The former CEO of Uber, Travis Kalanick, is one well-known individual who is known for using autocratic leadership. Uber's operations and strategic direction were tightly controlled by Kalanick, who frequently made choices that put rapid growth and competitive tactics ahead of teamwork or internal company culture. His time at Uber was characterized by notable growth achievements, but it also brought in a highly criticized workplace culture, difficulties with public relations, and multiple accusations of unethical behavior within the organization (Rizvi, 2024). Moreover, former CEO of Volkswagen, Martin Winterkorn, is also a business figure that is associated with the description of being a boss who dislikes failure or mistake. According to critics, Winterkorn's style had placed unnecessary pressure on to VW's managers that has led to one of the company's crisis of cheating in the US emission test for vehicles. In an article published by CNBC (2015), Volkswagen declined to give insights whether their own culture or the management style of Winterkorn had played a significant part in to that cheating. But Bernd Osterloh, a member of VW's supervisory board, released a letter to the staff with a content that the company is in need of an environment where problems are openly communicated to superiors. The same article cited that accounts from former VW's executives and observers describe the management style under Winterkorn is authoritarian and has planted fear among individuals. This only shows that proper balance must always be at checked and limitations are well-written to avoid developing problems in the workplace.

B. Democratic Leadership

Democratic leaders view their followers as fully capable of performing tasks independently. Instead of exerting control, they collaborate with their followers, striving to treat everyone fairly and not placing themselves above others. Essentially, they see themselves as guides rather than as authoritative figures (Woods, 2019). According to a study on job satisfaction in teaching, 67% of the best-performing schools use more democratic leadership styles (Hobbs, 2023). This kind of leadership exhibits characteristics such as being collaborative, adaptable, open-minded, and actively involved in the process. Strong democratic leaders cultivate trust and respect among their followers. They actively seek diverse perspectives and refrain from suppressing dissenting opinions or less popular viewpoints. Consequently, followers feel motivated to engage and contribute to the group's efforts (Cherry, 2024).

The establishment of an organizational culture rooted in democratic leadership principles yields a multitude of positive outcomes. Beyond the inherent encouragement of innovative solutions and the exploration of diverse problem-solving approaches, such a culture fosters a profound sense of loyalty among employees towards the organization (Cornell, 2024).

Democratic leaders are rational, focused, and masterful multitaskers. They excel at motivating teams and fostering inclusive decision-making. They value diverse perspectives, respect dissent, and prioritize transparency. Above all, they care deeply about employee growth and satisfaction (Quintana, 2022). Twitter's position as a prominent social media platform (Lindberg, 2023). Dorsey's leadership philosophy centers on the development and empowerment of team members, coupled with a commitment to accountability. He advocates for transparency regarding weaknesses and actively seeks to rectify them. This approach has played a significant role in propelling Twitter to its current position as a prominent social media platform (Lindberg, 2023).

There are some certain drawbacks with this kind of leadership. The decision-making process may take longer, especially if the group lacks the necessary skills or training, potentially leading to more difficulties in reaching the goal (Lee, 2023). Disagreements can arise when multiple opinions are involved, leading to conflicts or delays. Leaders must have strong facilitation skills to manage differing viewpoints and reach a resolution (Habba, 2024).

C. Transactional Leadership

In Transactional Leadership, Leaders frequently use a rewards system to motivate their teams. Transactional leadership taps into each team member's self-interest, motivating them to perform well in order to earn benefits or incentives (Martins, 2024). To inspire workers and uphold performance standards, transactional leadership uses rewards and penalties. In goal-oriented environments, like sales, and during emergencies where prompt, decisive action is required, this leadership style works well (Miroslavov, 2023).

Rewards and punishments serve as the primary motivation for subordinates to fulfill their duties and comply with directives, driving them to perform well and avoid errors. Clear standards and benchmarks for acceptable performance are established, with less emphasis on creativity and innovation; the priority lies in adhering to the leader's expectations. The organization's mission, systems, rules, and chain of command are fundamental to its structure, with leaders deriving their authority from their formal roles and responsibilities (Nasrudin, 2024).

Transactional leadership fosters a relationship between leaders and followers that ensures compliance with the leader's demands, though it may lack strong commitment to achievement. This constructive leadership style incorporates contingent rewards and management-by-exception. Transactional leaders establish clear expectations, offer feedback, and encourage employees to concentrate on fulfilling their job responsibilities (Udin et al., 2022). Howard Schultz did not found Starbucks, but he transformed it from a small business into a global phenomenon. He is credited with establishing the transactional business model that the company continues to use today. His determination and fortunate circumstances have contributed to his status as one of the wealthiest individuals in the United States (Bova, 2023).

Tim Parker exemplifies the contextual application of transactional leadership in addressing specific organizational challenges. He implemented swift changes by terminating individuals responsible for inefficiencies and restructuring the company. His decisive actions, driven by a system of rewards and punishments, introduced essential structure, resulting in a significant turnaround for AA and a marked increase in profits (Lindberg, 2022). Transactional leadership can hinder creativity and innovation due to its heavy reliance on routine and a rigid hierarchical structure, which discourages the emergence of new ideas. This leadership style often lacks an inspirational element, relying solely on extrinsic motivations without fostering emotional connections or a deeper organizational vision, leading to employees feeling disengaged. It assumes that all employees are motivated purely by rewards and punishments, neglecting their intrinsic psychological needs. Additionally, the purely transactional nature of the leader-subordinate relationship fails to cultivate loyalty or commitment, increasing turnover when workers lack emotional investment. Furthermore, its focus on short-term goals can undermine sustainable growth, as the structured processes and top-down hierarchies struggle to adapt to market changes or disruptions, ultimately hindering long-term strategic pivots (Skyles, 2024).

D. Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is a style that empowers individuals to create positive change through a compelling vision and inspiration. Transformational leaders create a vision for their followers and guide the change through inspiration and motivation. They are great role models, and many of their behaviors are imitated by their followers. Additionally, they motivate followers by boosting their self-efficacy, which gives them the confidence to surpass expectations (Farkas and Vera, 2014). Understanding people, identifying the objectives and desires of each team member, and uniting everyone to carry out change are all natural skills of transformational leaders (Joubert, 2024).

A transformational leader is characterized by a visionary mindset that prioritizes team cohesion and engagement. They inspire and motivate others while fostering an inclusive environment that values diverse perspectives. Their emotional intelligence allows them to connect deeply with team members, enhancing collaboration and creating a supportive atmosphere conducive to collective success (Joubert, 2023). Steve Jobs is a prime example of transformational leadership in the 21st century. His practices, such as wearing the same outfit daily to boost productivity and conceptualizing innovations like iCloud, were instrumental in Apple's

success. Under Jobs' influence, the company evolved from a product-focused identity to prioritizing services and brand loyalty. Today, Apple is valued at \$2 trillion, with continued growth anticipated in the coming years (Ugochukwu, 2024).

Leaders within this style foster change by emotionally connecting with their audience, motivating them to strive for something greater than themselves (Baker, 2023). A transformational leader sees opportunities for change, develops a strategy to bring about the change, and then motivates people to carry out the strategy. Their goal is to change the groups and companies they work with (Boogaard, 2024). This leadership approach promotes open and honest communication, empowering individuals to achieve new levels of personal development. It fosters a sense of responsibility and loyalty among participants, creating an environment conducive to innovation. Additionally, it builds a culture of mutual trust, enhancing collaboration and engagement within the organization (Telloian, 2022).

Transformational leadership can potentially exhaust individuals within the organization, as the drive for constant improvement and high expectations may lead to burnout. Furthermore, while visionaries can inspire, they may sometimes exhibit delusional thinking, becoming disconnected from practical realities. Additionally, leaders may become self-absorbed, prioritizing their vision over the needs and contributions of their team. Relying heavily on employees for innovation and support can also backfire, as it may lead to increased pressure and unrealistic expectations, ultimately undermining team morale and performance (Milicevic, 2024).

E. Laissez-Faire

Laissez-faire leaders provide their subordinates the freedom to run their own workstations and make their own judgments. When necessary, they provide support, direction, advice, and training to their team, but they rely on them to manage the specifics and carry out their assignments and projects. Key characteristics include the delegation of tasks, confidence in team members' capabilities, minimal guidance, fostering team autonomy, and generally low levels of feedback (Myers, 2024).

In settings where invention and originality are essential to success, laissez-faire leadership can be very successful. Laissez-faire leaders cultivate an environment that encourages creativity by allowing team members the liberty to experiment and take chances (Bova, 2023).

In this type of leadership, employees can experience an enhanced sense of ownership and pride in their work, contributing to greater motivation and job satisfaction. The opportunity to experiment and take risks can result in the generation of new ideas and innovative solutions. Also, the leaders are trusting the employees to make decisions in the organization that will lead into higher levels of engagement and empowerment. Lastly, employees are more likely to embrace the possibility of making mistakes without the fear of punitive consequences (Orduña, 2024).

Laissez-faire leadership has several notable disadvantages. It can lead to confusion and conflict when team members pursue individual objectives rather than a unified goal. Implementing this leadership style may be challenging, particularly in large organizations, where establishing trust and effective communication can be difficult. Additionally, laissez-faire leadership tends to be ineffective during crises, as decisive leadership is often required for quick decision-making. Lastly, it may result in lower overall productivity, as team members might lack motivation in the absence of supervision. In conclusion, the drawbacks of laissez-faire leadership include increased confusion and decreased productivity (Cherry, 2024).

F. Statement of the Problem

➤ *Describe the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of:*

- Sex
- Affiliation
- Position
- Length of Service

➤ *To Determine the Leadership Style Present in the Organization in Terms of:*

- Autocratic
- Democratic
- Transactional
- Transformational
- Laissez-Faire

➤ *To Determine the Leadership Engagement of Local Student Government in Terms of:*

- Job loyalty
- Job performance
- Turnover Intentions

➤ *Determine if there is a Significant Relationship between Leadership Styles and Engagement of Local Student Government*

➤ *Propose Strategies to Improve Engagement of Local Student Government based on the Results of the Study.*

G. Scope and Delimitation

This study aims to examine the relationship between different leadership styles commonly employed within the student government, assess their impact on member engagement and participation, and explore factors that may mediate this relationship. Fostering an environment that supports student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes requires effective leadership. Findings may not apply universally across all educational institutions due to varying cultures and structures. Limited sample size could affect the reliability of conclusions. Engagement and leadership efficacy can be subjective, influenced by personal experiences and perceptions of students. Leadership effectiveness may vary over time, influenced by changing student demographics, societal trends, or institutional policies.

The target population will consist of local student government key officers during the academic year 2024-2025, with data collected primarily through surveys questionnaires. The study will be conducted in NEUST – Sumacab Campus, located at Sumacab Este, Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija. We will be ensuring that the findings are relevant to this specific educational context.

H. Significance of the Study

- **Local Student Government.** Understanding how different leadership styles influence student engagement can lead to more effective governance structures. By identifying effective leadership practices, the study can help improve participation and investment in local student government, fostering a more active and involved student body.
- **Educational institutions and Policy makers.** The findings of this study may offer valuable insights for educational institutions and policymakers. By understanding which leadership styles drive student engagement, institutions can implement training and development programs for student leaders, as well as adapt their policies to promote more inclusive and participatory governance structures.
- **Teachers.** This research is vital for educators, leaders, and policymakers striving to foster an inclusive, engaging, and effective environment for student governance.
- **Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST).** This study may serve as one of the inputs for the project planning of the Extension Services Department to impart skills and technological training to the individuals in its adopted communities with limited access to formal education.
- **Future Researchers.** The study's outcome may serve as the initial groundwork for follow-up research in order to tackle the other business aspects and create an integrated set of knowledge as a basis to fully commercialize rabbit as a source of meat.

I. Definition of Terms

➤ *To Facilitate Better Understanding, the Following Key Terms were Defined Conceptually or Operationally:*

- **Autocratic leadership.** It is a style in which one leader holds complete control over decision-making and has total authority over the group or organization.
- **Democratic leadership.** It is also called participative leadership, is a style where the leader promotes input, cooperation, and active involvement from team members in the decision-making process.
- **Laissez-faire leadership.** It is a style where the leader adopts a hands-off approach, giving team members the freedom to make decisions and handle their own tasks with little interference or direction.
- **Local Student Government (LSG).** This refers to a student-run organization within a school or educational institution that represents the interests, concerns, and needs of the student body.
- **Job loyalty.** It refers to the level of commitment and dedication that student leaders, such as governor, vice governor, organization officers, committee heads and representatives have toward their roles and duties within the organization.
- **Job performance.** It refers to how effectively they carry out their duties and responsibilities within the organization.
- **Post-Action Review (PAR) Meetings.** These are reflective discussions that take place after a project, event, or activity to assess its effectiveness and results. The goal of a PAR meeting is to recognize what worked, what didn't, and how future actions can be enhanced.
- **Transactional leadership.** It is a leadership style that emphasizes supervision, organization, and performance. In this approach, leaders motivate team members and drive desired outcomes through the use of rewards and penalties.

- **Transformational leadership.** It is a style where leaders inspire and energize their team members to achieve outstanding results by cultivating a sense of purpose, passion, and dedication.
- **Turnover intentions.** This refers to the likelihood that student leaders, such as governor, vice governor, organization officers, committee heads and representatives will resign or leave their leadership positions.

CHAPTER THREE METHODS AND PROCEDURE

A. Research Design

This study uses a quantitative research approach as it is ideal for studying how leadership styles impact local student government engagement in Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology. It involves collecting numerical data through survey questionnaire, then proceeding with the statistical analysis. This approach helps to identify how different leadership styles—such as autocratic, democratic, transformational, transactional, or laissez-faire—affect student loyalty, satisfaction, and turnover intention. By using the Likert scale for responses, the methodology allowed for a detailed assessment through statistical analysis, providing evidence to guide the development of better leadership strategies.

This research employs a descriptive research design to examine the effectiveness of leadership styles in engaging local student government. Initially, secondary data were collected from a variety of sources, including books, academic journals, and online resources.

B. Locale of the Study

The Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST) Sumacab Campus is an ideal research site for studying the efficacy of leadership styles in the engagement of local student government. This site will serve as the location where data is gathered from local student government key officers, providing insights into how various leadership styles influence engagement, participation, and governance within the student government of NEUST. With its multiple courses and student organizations, the university offers a rich environment to explore how different leadership styles influence student involvement and governance. It also provides accessibility to the researchers since they were graduates of the said university. It will be feasible to gather data through surveys, interviews, or observations of leadership practices within the university's student governance system.

Fig 1: Map of Nueva ECIJA University of Science and Technology-Sumacab Campus, Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija

C. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the key officials of the Local Student Government. These are the Governor, Vice Governor, Secretary, Treasurer, Auditor, Business Manager, Public Information Officer, Representative, and Judicial Representative. Their views on leadership styles are essential, as they both influence and are shaped by different approaches. They offer valuable insights into how leadership affects their effectiveness, team dynamics, and engagement.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents According to Affiliation

Local Student Government	Frequency
Atate Student Gov.	9
Carranglan Student Gov.	9
College of Architecture Student Gov.	9
College of Arts and Sciences Student Gov.	9
College of Criminology Student Gov.	9
College of Education Student Gov.	9
College of Engineering Student Gov.	9
College of Industrial Tech. Student Gov.	9
College of Info. & Comm. Tech. Student Gov.	9
College of Mngmt. & Buss. Tech. Student Gov.	9
College of Nursing Student Gov.	9
College of Public Admin. & Dis. Mngmt. Student Gov.	9
Fort Magsaysay Student Gov.	9
Gabalton Student Gov.	9
Laboratory High School Student Gov.	9
Papaya Student Gov.	9
Penaranda Student Gov.	9
San Isidro Student Gov.	9
San Antonio Student Gov.	9
San Leonardo Student Gov.	9
Sto. Domingo Student Gov.	9
Talavera Student Gov.	9
Total	198
Sample size	102

D. Sampling Procedure

This study will use the purposive sampling method and it is suitable when the research focuses specifically on a particular group—in this case, the personnel who hold positions within the student government of NEUST. Since the goal is to explore how different leadership styles affect their engagement and participation, purposive sampling allows the researcher to intentionally select individuals who have direct involvement in leadership roles. Purposive sampling is a method where researchers choose participants based on specific characteristics, experiences, or other criteria relevant to the population of interest. This selected sample serves as representatives for the broader group or population being studied (Stratton, 2024).

The reason for choosing the purposive sampling method is that the researchers can specifically target those who have varying levels of exposure to different leadership styles. These members are the most knowledgeable about leadership dynamics within the student government.

E. Research Instrument

In order to answer the problem stipulated in this research, data was gathered from respondents using survey questionnaires which is defined as a document containing set of questions or prompts designed to collect relevant information from a respondent. There will be structured questions with pre-determined and close-ended responses that respondents can choose from. Survey questionnaires is best for large population where interview is impractical and can provide data for easy statistical analysis needed for drawing objectives conclusions and/or recommendations.

F. Data Collection Procedure

The researchers collected primary data by employing survey questionnaires to the key officials of the NEUST Local Student Government. The research instrument shall undergo evaluation to ensure that the content is strictly related to measuring the perspective of the said respondents to the efficacy of leadership style in their organization. After the validation, the researchers seek for the approval of the research teacher to conduct the survey. After the approval, the researchers personally and virtually administered the questionnaires to the target respondents. Meanwhile, secondary data essential for this study such as the total number of populations of the city was obtained through visiting online website and published journal.

G. Data Analysis Techniques

The responses of the respondents to the survey questionnaire were meticulously tallied, tabulated and organized. The data presented, analyzed, and interpreted with the use of weighted mean, frequency counts, percentage, and ranking system.

➤ *Percentage*

$$\% = F/n \times 100\%$$

Where:

% = Percentage

F = Number of Respondents

N = total number of respondents

➤ *Average Weighted Mean*

$$AWM = 4F+3F+2F+1F/n$$

Where:

F = Stands for number of frequencies for the corresponding scale

N = total number of respondents

Table 2: Basis of Verbal Interpretation

Weight	Scale	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 and above	4	Strongly Agree
2.50 - 3.49	3	Agree
1.50 - 2.49	2	Disagree
Below 1.50	1	Strongly Disagree

H. Ethical Considerations

➤ *Informed Consent and Participation Risks that May Affect the Autonomy and Well-Being of Participants.*

➤ *To Address Issues:*

- Provide Clear Information
- Secure Informed Consent
- Allow Withdrawal

➤ *Data Privacy and Confidentiality Concerns that May Jeopardize the Privacy and Security of Participant Information.*

➤ *To Address Issues:*

- Secure Data Storage
- Restrict Access
- Safely Dispose of Data

➤ *Ethical Conduct and Integrity Concerns About Conducting the Research With Honesty, Transparency and Integrity.*

➤ *To Address Issues:*

- Report Findings Honestly
- Acknowledge Contributions

CHAPTER FOUR RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the information gathered from the implementation and conduction of survey questionnaires. The responses were organized, quantified, and interpreted using different statistical tools. The order of presentation followed the sequence of problems enumerated in this study.

A. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents According to Sex

Sex	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Male	53	50%
Female	52	49.1%
Other	1	0.9%
Total	106	100%

Table 3 shows the profile of the responding according to sex. It can be seen that majority of the respondents are male with a frequency of 53 and percentage of 50. Females (49.1%) and other sex category (0.9%) constitute the remaining portion of the total number of respondents.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents According to Affiliation

Local Student Government	Frequency	Percentage
Atate Student Gov.	8	7.5%
Carranglan Student Gov.	0	0
College of Architecture Student Gov.	4	3.8%
College of Arts and Sciences Student Gov.	5	4.7%
College of Criminology Student Gov.	8	7.5%
College of Education Student Gov.	6	5.7%
College of Engineering Student Gov.	10	9.4%
College of Industrial Tech. Student Gov.	6	5.7%
College of Info. & Comm. Tech. Student Gov.	11	10.4%
College of Mngmt. & Buss. Tech. Student Gov.	8	7.5%
College of Nursing Student Gov.	3	2.8%
College of Public Admin. & Dis. Mngmt. Student Gov.	0	0
Fort Magsaysay Student Gov.	4	3.8%
Gabalton Student Gov.	9	8.5%
Laboratory High School Student Gov.	6	5.7%
Papaya Student Gov.	1	0.9%
Penaranda Student Gov.	1	0.9%
San Isidro Student Gov.	3	2.8%
San Antonio Student Gov.	3	2.8%
San Leonardo Student Gov.	2	1.9%
Sto. Domingo Student Gov.	3	2.8%
Talavera Student Gov.	5	4.7%
Total	106	100%

Table 4 indicates the affiliation or the organization in which the respondents belong to. The College of Information and Communications Technology is observable to contribute the highest followed by College of Engineering, and Gabaldon Campus Student Government. Nevertheless, it can also be seen that responses are well distributed which implied good representation to all local student governments in NEUST.

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents According to Position

Positions Held	Frequency	Percentage
Governor	16	15.1%
Vice Governor	8	7.5%
Secretary	5	4.7%
Treasurer	10	9.4%
Auditor	6	5.7%
Business Manager	4	3.8%

PIO	9	8.5%
Representative	11	10.4%
Judicial	5	4.7%
Prefer not say	32	30.2%
Total	106	100%

Table 5 describes the respondents’ held position in the local student government. Most of the participation in the study is coming from LSG Personnel who wishes not to reveal their position with frequency and percentage of 32 and 30.2%. The second highest are the governors followed by representatives with a combined percentage of 45.3%.

Table 6: Distribution of Respondents According to Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
Less than one year	40	37.7%
1 year	14	13.2%
2 years	37	34.9%
3 years	14	13.2%
4 years	1	0.9%
More than four years	0	0%
Total	106	100%

Table 6 provides data on the length of service rendered by local student governments’ personnel in their respective organizations. It shows that most respondents are new to their group with less than one year of service rendered. Second to the highest are personnel with two years experience with frequency and percentage of 37 and 34.9%.

B. Leadership Style Present in the Organization

Table 7: Autocratic

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The leaders make decisions without consulting members.	1.64	D
There is a lack of opportunity for discussion or feedback with the decision-making.	1.85	D
Team members are expected to follow directives without question.	1.98	D
I hesitate to express my opinions during team meetings	2.0	D
Average Weighted Mean	1.87	D

Table 7 shows the assessment of the respondents’ experiences to the concept of autocratic leadership. It can be seen that the respondents disagree to the following statements: The leaders make decisions without consulting member; There is a lack of opportunity for discussion or feedback with the decision-making; Team members are expected to follow directives without question; and I hesitate to express my opinions during team meetings. With weighted means of 1.64, 1.85, 1.98, and 2.0 respectively.

The overall weighted mean is 1.87 which means that the respondents disagree that autocratic leadership style is being experience in their organization.

Table 8: Democratic

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Members are encouraged to share their opinions before the decisions were made.	3.59	SA
Collaboration is often present and recommended in the organization.	3.57	SA
Group discussions play a significant role in our decision-making.	3.63	SA
The leaders often seek feedback from members on important issues.	3.52	SA
Average Weighted Mean	3.58	SA

Table 8 shows the assessment of the respondents’ experiences to the concept of democratic leadership. Respondents shown strong agreement to all of the statements above, namely: Members are encouraged to share their opinions before the decisions were made; Collaboration is often present and recommended in the organization; Group discussions play a significant role in our decision-making; and the leaders often seek feedback from members on important issues. With respective weighted means of 3.59, 3.57, 3.63, and 3.52 each.

The overall weighted mean is 3.58, which only indicates that respondents strongly agree that democratic leadership style is being experienced in their organization.

Table 9: Transactional

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The leaders provide clear expectations and performance metrics.	2.98	A
Rewards and recognition are tied to specific performance results.	2.92	A
The members receive feedback on their performance regularly.	2.93	A
The leaders emphasize to strictly obey the established rules and regulations.	3.07	A
Average Weighted Mean	2.97	A

Table 9 shows the assessment of the respondents’ experiences to the concept of transactional leadership. It can be observed that the responds all agree to the following statements: the leaders provide clear expectations and performance metrics; Rewards and recognition are tied to specific performance results; the members receive feedback on their performance regularly; and the leaders emphasize to strictly obey the established rules and regulations. Furthermore, each statements mentioned earned 2.98, 2.92, 2.93, and 3.07 respective weighted means.

With 2.97 total average weighted mean, the respondents agree that the concept of transactional leadership is existing within their organization.

Table 10: Transformational

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The leaders are inspiring the members to go beyond their self-interest for the sake of the organization.	2.84	A
Leaders encourage personal & prof. growth among members.	2.83	A
I feel motivated to contribute to the organization’s vision and goals.	2.87	A
The leaders are genuinely concerned about my well-being and development.	2.84	A
Average Weighted Mean	2.85	A

Table 10 shows the assessment of the respondents’ experiences to the concept of transformational leadership. Respondents agree to the statements: the leaders are inspiring the members to go beyond their self-interest for the sake of the organization; leaders encourage personal & professional growth among members; I feel motivated to contribute to the organization’s vision and goals; and the leaders are genuinely concerned about my well-being and development. 2.84, 2.83, 2.87, and 2.84 are the individual weighted means of the above-mentioned statements.

The total average weighted mean is 2.85 or synonymous to the respondents agreeing that they also experience transformational leadership style in their organization.

Table 11: Laissez-Faire

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The leaders are allowing the members to work and decide independently regarding their tasks.	2.46	D
The leaders provide minimal guidance, allowing members to find solutions on their own.	2.30	D
The leaders intervene only when it’s absolutely necessary.	2.23	D
Members feel that they can explore their innovative ideas without fear of criticism.	2.62	A
Average Weighted Mean	2.40	D

Table 11 shows the assessment of the respondents’ experiences to the concept of laissez-faire leadership. The statement “members feel that they can explore their innovative ideas without fear of criticism” got the highest weighted mean of 2.62. Meanwhile, the respondents show disarrangement to the following statements: the leaders are allowing the members to work and decide independently regarding their tasks; the leaders provide minimal guidance, allowing members to find solutions on their own; and the leaders intervene only when it’s absolutely necessary, with weighted means of 2.46, 2.30. and 2.23 each.

The overall weighted mean is 2.40. This means that the respondents disagree to the presence or laissez-faire style of leadership in their team.

C. Engagement of Local Student Government Personnel

Table 12: Job Loyalty

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I feel a strong commitment to my student government role.	3.30	A
I am willing to invest additional time and effort into the organization	3.38	A
I envision myself staying in this organization for the long term.	3.25	A
I actively promote my organization to others.	3.33	A
Average Weighted Mean	3.31	A

Table 12 exhibit the job loyalty of the respondents. The respondents agree to the following statements: I feel a strong commitment to my student government role; I am willing to invest additional time and effort into the organization; I envision myself staying in this organization for the long term; and I actively promote my organization to others. Weighted mean for each statement is 3.30, 3.38, 3.25, and 3.33.

The aggregate average weighted mean is computed at 3.31. This translate to the notion that respondent agree that they are loyal to their Job as Local Student Government Personnel.

Table 13: Job Performance

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I feel that my contributions were valued in the organization.	3.14	A
I regularly complete my tasks and responsibilities on time.	3.12	A
I am able to meet the standards and expectations of my role within the organization	3.08	A
I collaborate effectively with my fellow members to achieve our goals.	3.26	A
Average Weighted Mean	3.15	A

Table 13 exhibit the job performance of the respondents. The statements: I feel that my contributions were valued in the organization; I regularly complete my tasks and responsibilities on time; I am able to meet the standards and expectations of my role within the organization; and I collaborate effectively with my fellow members to achieve our goals, all got a verbal interpretation of “agree” due to their weighted means of 3.14, 3.12, 3.08, and 3.26.

With an average total weighted mean of 3.15, respondents agreed that they engage and perform in the organization.

Table 14: Turnover Intention

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I often feel dissatisfied with my role within the organization.	1.72	D
I have considered leaving my position if given the chance.	1.76	D
I often think about stepping back because of my responsibilities given to me in the local student government	1.97	D
I am not happy with the organization any more.	1.73	D
Average Weighted Mean	1.79	D

Table 14 exhibit the turnover intention of the respondents. The respondents disagree to the statements: I often feel dissatisfied with my role within the organization; I have considered leaving my position if given the chance; I often think about stepping back because of my responsibilities given to me in the local student government; and I am not happy with the organization any more. Recorded weighted means are 1.72, 1.76, 1.97, and 1.73 respectively.

The calculated total average weighted mean is 1.79 which illustrates that respondents disagree to turnover intentions.

D. Relationship between Leadership Styles and Engagement of Local Student Government Personnel

Table 15: Relationship between Leadership Styles and Engagement of LSG Personnel

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Leadership style has a direct impact to my engagement and/or participation levels in the organization.	3.68	SA
Average Weighted Mean	3.68	SA

Table 15 display the relationship between leadership styles and the levels of engagement of local student government personnel. It shows that respondents strongly agree that leadership style has an impact to the engagement to their organization.

E. Strategies for Improvement

The following strategies are derived and formulated for the further improvement of operating the local student governments.

➤ *Establish a Participatory Governance Structure*

Transition from a conventional top-down leadership structure to a more inclusive approach, where leadership responsibilities are distributed, and decision-making is a collective process.

Incorporating the input of people or organizations impacted by your policy, legislation, or service increases the likelihood of success by leveraging the experience, expertise, and motivations of the communities served. Engaging diverse perspectives, especially those outside your organization, ensures more inclusive design and greater potential to benefit a wider range of people (Andrews, 2019).

Based on the results, democratic leadership is the most applied among the LSG. With this, organizations should establish a participatory governance where students can properly engage and be more inclusive.

➤ *Transparency and Responsibility*

Based on the results, transparency and responsibility can foster trust and guarantee openness in all areas of student government activities. Encouraging the members to express their ideas before deciding a course of action. Valuing their feedback and wanting to improve something. With this. Leaders can build a culture of transparency that fosters trust, accountability, and collaboration within their teams. Based on a study, 40% of people are disengaged when they receive little or no feedback. Timely, relevant feedback fosters intrinsic motivation, driving individuals to self-motivate, improve performance, and continue learning (Workleap, 2014).

➤ *Implementing Creative Thinking*

Based on the results, incorporating lateral and divergent thinking could facilitate the smooth functioning of the democratic leadership style. School organizations should implement creative thinking because it enables student leaders to be challenged and grasp complex problems that may arise in organizations. While lateral thinking follows a structured, step-by-step approach, introducing divergent thinking can foster a collaborative environment, engaging the team through brainstorming sessions.

Lateral thinking enhances adaptability and fosters innovation, especially as new technologies and changing workforce demands make products and processes obsolete quickly. Lateral thinking provides a framework for innovation, enabling teams to explore novel solutions, stay ahead of competitors, and potentially drive disruptive change (Miles, 2023).

➤ *Foster a Culture of Collaboration and Consensus*

Results show that students collaborate effectively with their fellow members to achieve their goals. To strengthen an organizational culture, school organizations should demonstrate collaboration by working together, seeking input and valuing diverse perspectives. Promote decision-making through consensus-building instead of relying on majority rule, ensuring that every voice is heard and valued.

➤ *Post-Action Review (PAR) Meetings*

Based on the results, there is an opportunity for students to express their opinions, suggestions and solutions freely during meetings. School organizations should schedule regular post-action review meetings following the completion of major projects or activities. These meetings should aim to evaluate what was successful, what challenges arose, and the reasons behind both outcomes.

The PAR tool, introduced in 1970 for military use, was designed to systematize learning and view each activity as an opportunity for new insights. It has since proven effective in knowledge management across various sectors, from profit-driven organizations to policymaking. It helps shape organizational culture by promoting the value that "our strength is knowledge" (Dumanovic et al., 2022).

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings based on the presented data, conclusions drawn from the analysis and summary of findings, and recommendations offered based on the results of the study.

A. Summary

The following are the findings of the study:

➤ Profile of the Respondents

- **Sex.** 50% of the respondents are male, 49.1% are females, and 0.9 % of the respondents are other gender category.
- **Affiliation.** Most or 10.4% of the respondents are from the college of information and communications technology; 9.4% came from the College of Engineering; 8.5% came from Gabaldon Campus; Atate Campus, College of Criminology, and College of Management and Business Technology each contributed 7.5%; College of Industrial Technology, College of Education, and Laboratory High School each contributed 5.7%; College of Arts and Sciences and Talavera Off-Campus each contributed 4.7%; College of Architecture and Fort Magsaysay Campus each contributed 3.8%; College of Nursing, San Isidro Campus, San Antonio Off-Campus, and Sto. Domingo Campus contributed 2.8%; San Leonardo shared 1.9% of the total respondents; and Papaya Off-Campus, and Penaranda Off-Campus each contributes 0.9%.
- **Position.** 30.2% of the respondents choose not to reveal their positions. 15.1% of the respondents are identified as a governor; 10.4% are representatives; 9.4% are treasurers; 8.5% are public information officers; 7.5% are vice governors; 5.7% are auditors; Judicial representatives and Secretaries each contributed 4.7%; and the lowest percentage of respondents goes to business managers.
- **Length of Service.** Majority or 37.7% of the respondents have less than a year in service; 34.9% of respondents have two years length of service; respondents with one year and three years of service length each contributed 13.2%; and 0.9% percent have four years length of service.

➤ Leadership Style Present in the Organization

• Autocratic

Respondents disagree to the following statements: The leaders make decisions without consulting member; There is a lack of opportunity for discussion or feedback with the decision-making; Team members are expected to follow directives without question; and I hesitate to express my opinions during team meetings. With weighted means of 1.64, 1.85, 1.98, and 2.0 respectively.

• Democratic

Respondents strongly agree to the statements: Members are encouraged to share their opinions before the decisions were made; Collaboration is often present and recommended in the organization; Group discussions play a significant role in our decision-making; and the leaders often seek feedback from members on important issues. With respective weighted means of 3.59, 3.57, 3.63, and 3.52 each.

• Transactional

Respondents agree to the following statements: the leaders provide clear expectations and performance metrics; Rewards and recognition are tied to specific performance results; the members receive feedback on their performance regularly; and the leaders emphasize to strictly obey the established rules and regulations. Furthermore, each statements mentioned earned 2.98, 2.92, 2.93, and 3.07 respective weighted means.

• Transformational

Respondents agree to the statements: the leaders are inspiring the members to go beyond their self-interest for the sake of the organization; leaders encourage personal & professional growth among members; I feel motivated to contribute to the organization's vision and goals; and the leaders are genuinely concerned about my well-being and development. 2.84, 2.83, 2.87, and 2.84 are the individual weighted means of the above-mentioned statements.

• Laissez-Faire

The statement "members feel that they can explore their innovative ideas without fear of criticism" got the highest weighted mean of 2.62. Meanwhile, the respondents show disarrangement to the following statements: the leaders are allowing the members to work and decide independently regarding their tasks; the leaders provide minimal guidance, allowing members to find solutions on their own; and the leaders intervene only when it's absolutely necessary, with weighted means of 2.46, 2.30. and 2.23 each.

➤ *Leadership Engagement of Local Student Government*

• *Job Loyalty*

The respondents agree to the following statements: I feel a strong commitment to my student government role; I am willing to invest additional time and effort into the organization; I envision myself staying in this organization for the long term; and I actively promote my organization to others. Weighted mean for each statement is 3.30, 3.38, 3.25, and 3.33.

• *Job Performance*

The statements: I feel that my contributions were valued in the organization; I regularly complete my tasks and responsibilities on time; I am able to meet the standards and expectations of my role within the organization; and I collaborate effectively with my fellow members to achieve our goals, all got a verbal interpretation of “agree” due to their weighted means of 3.14, 3.12, 3.08, and 3.26.

• *Turnover Intention*

The respondents disagree to the statements: I often feel dissatisfied with my role within the organization; I have considered leaving my position if given the chance; I often think about stepping back because of my responsibilities given to me in the local student government; and I am not happy with the organization any more. Recorded weighted means are 1.72, 1.76, 1.97, and 1.73 respectively.

➤ *Relationship of Leadership Style and Engagement in Local Student Government*

The respondents strongly agree that leadership style has an impact to the engagement to their organization.

B. Conclusions

➤ *Based on the Summary of Findings, the Researchers Concluded the Following:*

- Majority of the local student government are male.
- Most of the responses came from Local Student Government situated in NEUST Sumacab Campus.
- Large Percentile of Responses are anonymous.
- Local Student Government holds young-bloods or those leaders with less than a year of experience.
- Respondents disagree to the existence of autocratic leadership style in their organization.
- Respondents strongly agree to the existence of democratic leadership style in their organization.
- Respondents agree to the existence of transactional leadership style in their organization.
- Respondents agree to the existence of transformational leadership style in their organization.
- Respondents disagree to the existence of laissez-faire leadership style in their organization.
- Respondents agree that they are loyal to their job and organization.
- Respondents agree that they perform well in their job and organization.
- Respondents disagree they have turnover intentions.
- Respondents strongly agree that engagement into organization is influenced at large by the existing leadership style.

C. Recommendations

After the careful analysis of the data, the researchers recommended the following:

Seminars should be given to the local student government with focus to the different leadership styles, its key advantage and disadvantages, and each suitability to the organizations' context. It should be held in other campus that show low trends of participants

To even further the democratic values in organization - all key officials are hereby recommended to be elected rather than appointed as prescribed by the election code of USG constitution and by-laws

Every undertaking should be formalized as much as possible. All key officials of LSGs must receive and signature their office orders to have clear expectations to their duties, responsibilities, and roles in the organization. This also goes beyond on communication that include drafting formal letters, notice, and resolutions

Leadership shouldn't only be the entire focus of joining the local student government. Holistic development of an individual should be given emphasis as well. Seminars, trainings, and workshops regarding timely topics like personal finance, emotional management, stress management, career path analysis, and the like must be given to these personnel. Proposals to recreation and relaxation or team building activities is to be encouraged as well.

Breathing room or little freedom must be given on to the personnel. Those with commanding powers should be careful to fall into the trap of micromanagement that only brings unnecessary pressure that can lead to discouragement.

Personnel can be given the task to create their own project and unique program to the LSG like creation of set of standards in different areas of LSG including financial management and procurement. Doing this can make the personnel feel more connected to the LSG because they have contributed something of their own. It can ultimately make them feel valuable and important that makes them don't want to leave the organization.

Establishing of the culture of treating each other in the LSG as family can do much in terms of their capacity to do or perform their job well. This means that a reward system can be beneficial to all. Words of affirmation, recognition, or small tokens of appreciation can kindle the flame of inspiration in these leaders to continue their volunteer works. Treating one another as family can also reflect upon understanding and gentle correction of mistakes.

Fortunately, the study found out that there is a little to no turnover intention. Maintaining this good stature can be done by the initiative of reducing pressure and amount of workload. Inviting or recruiting of additional members to have more delegation of task can be a step towards this

LSG should include in their interview the asking of the preferred leadership style of any applicants. This is very important in the establishment of sound working environment in the local student government which is important in promoting engagement and participation.

Repetition and/or Replication of this study in different set of target respondents or locale.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ahmed, S., Simha, A. (2023). Autocratic Leadership and Abuse. In: Poff, D.C., Michalos, A.C. (eds) Encyclopedia of Business and Professional Ethics. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-22767-8_1300
- [2]. Andrews, P. (2019, October 17). *Participatory public governance: why we need it, what it is, and how to do it (in that order)*. The Mandarin. <https://www.themandarin.com.au/118165-participatory-public-governance-why-we-need-it-what-it-is-and-how-to-do-it-in-that-order/>
- [3]. Baker, C. (2023, January 5). What is transformational leadership?. Leaders.com. <https://leaders.com/articles/leadership/transformational-leadership/>
- [4]. Batista-Taran, L. C., Shuck, M. B., Gutierrez, C. C., & Sofia Baralt Florida International University, USA. (2013). The role of leadership style in employee engagement. *The Role of Leadership Style in Employee Engagement*. <https://digitalcommons.fiu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1143&context=sferc/>
- [5]. Boogaard, K. (2024, February 14). Transformational leadership: Definition, examples, tips. Work Life by Atlassian. <https://www.atlassian.com/blog/leadership/how-transformational-leadership-can-better-your-company>
- [6]. Bova, D. (2023, January 26). What is transactional leadership - and how does it work?. Entrepreneur. <https://www.entrepreneur.com/starting-a-business/what-is-transactional-leadership-and-how-does-it-work/443667>
- [7]. Bova, D. (2023, April 19). What is laissez faire leadership? what are its benefits and drawbacks?. Entrepreneur. <https://www.entrepreneur.com/leadership/what-is-laissez-faire-leadership-what-are-its-benefits-and/449201>
- [8]. Briker, R. (2020, May). Hurry Up! the role of supervisors' time urgency and self-perceived status for autocratic leadership and subordinates' well-being. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341485384_Hurry_Up_the_role_of_supervisors_time_urgency_and_self-perceived_status_for_autocratic_leadership_and_subordinates_well-being
- [9]. Brown, G. (2024, June 28). What is autocratic leadership? characteristics, pros and cons. Niagara Institute. <https://www.niagarainstitute.com/blog/autocratic-leadership-style>
- [10]. Bwalya, A. R. (2023, August). (PDF) leadership styles. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373068669_LEADERSHIP_STYLES
- [11]. Cherry, K. (2023, June 27). What are the pros and cons of autocratic leadership?. Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-autocratic-leadership-2795314#:~:text=Autocratic%20leadership%2C%20also%20known%20as%20authoritarian%20leadership%2C%20is%20a,and%20judgments%20and%20rarely%20accept%20advice%20from%20followers.>
- [12]. Cherry, K. (2024, June 19). Is Democratic leadership the best style of leadership?. Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-democratic-leadership-2795315>
- [13]. Cherry, K. (2024, August 29). Laissez-faire leadership advantages and disadvantages. Explore Psychology. https://www.explorepsychology.com/laissez-faire-leadership-advantages/#Laissez-Faire_Leadership_Disadvantages
- [14]. CNBC. (2015, October 11). Fear and respect: VW's culture under Winterkorn. <https://www.cnbc.com/2015/10/11/emissions-scandal-vws-demanding-culture-under-winterkorn-led-to-crisis.html>
- [15]. Cornell, D., & Drew, C. (2024, January 3). 17 Democratic Leadership Examples & Characteristics. Helpful Professor. <https://helpfulprofessor.com/democratic-leadership-examples/>
- [16]. Feder, M. (2022, September 5). Laissez-faire leadership: Definition and examples. University of Phoenix. <https://www.phoenix.edu/blog/what-is-laissez-faire-leadership-style.html>
- [17]. Farkas, F. B., & Vera, A. (2014, November). Power and Transformational Leadership in public organizations. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273186255_Power_and_transformational_leadership_in_public_or_ganizations
- [18]. Gavin, M. (2019, October 22). Common styles of Leadership & How To Identify Yours. Business Insights Blog. <https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/styles-of-leadership>
- [19]. Gutterman, A. S. (2023, May). (PDF) definitions and conceptions of leadership. Definitions and Conceptions of Leadership. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371169414_Definitions_and_Conceptions_of_Leadership
- [20]. Habba, A. (2024, September 16). *Autocratic vs. Democratic leadership: Pros, cons, and best practices*. Medium. <https://alinahabba.medium.com/autocratic-vs-democratic-leadership-pros-cons-and-best-practices-0da078e6cf8f>
- [21]. Hobbs, G. (2023, July). Master democratic leadership: A new manager's Guide to Success. Master Democratic Leadership: A New Manager's Guide to Success. <https://www.lepaya.com/blog/democratic-leadership>
- [22]. IMD. (2024, October 11). The 6 most common leadership styles & how to find yours. IMD business school for management and leadership courses. <https://www.imd.org/blog/leadership/leadership-styles/>
- [23]. Indeed Editorial Team. (2024, September 24). What is the importance of leadership? | indeed.com. What Is the Importance of Leadership? <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/importance-of-leadership>
- [24]. Joubert, S. (2023). Transformational Leadership Style: How To Inspire And Motivate. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/what-is-transformational-leadership.html#Examples-of-transformational-leaders>
- [25]. Joubert, S. (2024, July 25). *Transformational leadership: How to inspire innovation in the Workplace*. Graduate Blog. <https://graduate.northeastern.edu/resources/transformational-leadership/>
- [26]. Krus, K. (2013a, April 9). *What is Leadership*. Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/kevinkruse/>
- [27]. Lee, S. (2024, July 1). The style of Democratic leadership. Torch. <https://torch.io/blog/what-is-democratic-leadership/>

- [28]. Lindberg, C. (2023, January 18). Famous examples of the Democratic Leadership Style. Leadership Ahoy! <https://www.leadershipahoy.com/famous-examples-of-the-democratic-leadership-style/>
- [29]. Lindberg, C. (2022, August 18). Transactional leadership - explained by a CEO. Leadership Ahoy! <https://www.leadershipahoy.com/transactional-leadership-what-is-it-pros-cons-examples/>
- [30]. Mansaray, H. E. (2019, June). The Role of Leadership Style in Organisational Change Management: A Literature Review. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334486140_The_Role_of_Leadership_Style_in_Organisational_Change_Management_A_Literature_Review
- [31]. Malec, M. (2022, December 20). Autocratic leadership: A guide for workplace management. RSS. <https://www.learnerbly.com/articles/autocratic-leadership>
- [32]. Martins, J. (2024, February 5). What is transactional leadership? is it effective? [2024] • asana. Asana. <https://asana.com/resources/transactional-leadership-benefits-and-uses>. Psych Central. <https://psychcentral.com/health/transformational-leadership>
- [33]. Maseti, Z., & Gumede, N. (2011, December 1). Contemporary perspectives on autocratic leadership. Sabinet. <https://journals.co.za/doi/abs/10.10520/EJC67283/>
- [34]. Miles, M. (2023, May 25). *What is Lateral Thinking? Definition & 7 Techniques to Do It Right*. Wwww.betterup.com. <https://www.betterup.com/blog/what-is-lateral-thinking>
- [35]. Milicevic, O. (2023, July 28). Transformational leadership: Benefits & weaknesses. Pumble Blog. <https://pumble.com/blog/transformational-leadership/#weaknesses-of-transformational-leadership>
- [36]. Miroslavov, M. (2023, December 18). Transform your leadership style: Inspiring examples of transactional leadership at work. OfficeRnD. <https://www.officernd.com/blog/examples-of-transactional-leadership/>
- [37]. Nasrudin, A., & About Ahmad Nasrudin I am an introspective writer with a strong passion for storytelling and a keen analytical mind. Drawing on my experience in equity research and credit risk. (2024, August 18). Transactional leadership: Meaning, examples, characteristics, Pros, cons. Penpoin. <https://penpoin.com/transactional-leadership/>
- [38]. National Geographic Society. (2023). Autocracy. Education. <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/autocracy/>
- [39]. Orduña, C. (2024, July 1). Everything you should know about laissez-faire leadership. CareerMinds. <https://careerminds.com/blog/laissez-faire-leadership>
- [40]. Parsons, L. (2024, May 31). How to determine what my leadership style is - professional & executive development: Harvard DCE. Professional & Executive Development | Harvard DCE. <https://professional.dce.harvard.edu/blog/how-to-determine-what-my-leadership-style-is/>
- [41]. Quintana, C. (2022, February 9). Why Democratic leadership is the best style to boost productivity [really]. The Management Blog by Beebole. <https://beebole.com/blog/why-democratic-leadership-is-the-best-style-to-boost-productivity/>
- [42]. Rizvi, H. (2024, September 6). Travis Kalanick Leadership style: Navigating the storm. Hidayat Rizvi. <https://hidayatrizvi.com/travis-kalanick-leadership-style/>
- [43]. Sindakis, S. (2024, September 16). Autocratic leadership: Examining the pros and cons of command and Control. Academia World News. <https://academiaworldnews.com/autocratic-leadership-examining-the-pros-and-cons-of-command-and-control/>
- [44]. Skyes, J. (2024, April 21). Transactional leadership: Advantages and disadvantages – humans of Globe. Recognizing the Success of Today's Leaders | Humans of Globe. <https://humansofglobe.com/transactional-leadership-advantage-disadvantages/>
- [45]. Telloian, C. (2022, June 22). Transformational leadership: Characteristics, benefits, and uses. Psych Central. <https://psychcentral.com/health/transformational-leadership>
- [46]. Udin, Isalman, & Dananjoyo, R. (2022, June). The effect of transactional leadership on Innovative Work Behavior: Testing the role of knowledge sharing and work engagement as mediation variables. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361066326_The_Effect_of_Transactional_Leadership_on_Innovative_Work_Behavior_Testing_the_Role_of_Knowledge_Sharing_and_Work_Engagement_as_Mediation_Variables
- [47]. Woods, P. A. (2019). Democratic Leadership. https://uhra.herts.ac.uk/bitstream/handle/2299/23539/Democratic_Leadership_revised_final_Jan2019.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- [48]. Workleap. (2014, October 7). *Statistics on the importance of employee feedback*. Workleap. <https://workleap.com/blog/infographic-employee-feedback/>
- [49]. Vukanović-Dumanović, V., Avlijaš, G., & Jokić, S. (2022). After Action Review as a tool for implementation of the knowledge management program. *Ekonomika*, 68(4), 29–40. <https://doi.org/10.5937/ekonomika2204029v>